

COUNTERFEIT CURRENCY DETECTION USING CNN AND IMAGE PROCESSING TECHNIQUES

Dr D Radhika¹, G Amrutha Sriya², Prof Vasala Madhava Rao³

¹Associate Professor CSE Stanley College of Engineering and Technology for Women, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

²BE CSE Student, Stanley College of Engineering & Technology for Women, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

³Research Professor, GIET University, Gunupur, Odisha, India

ABSTRACT

Counterfeit currency is a constant threat to the economy, and innovative and automated detection methods for preventing loss and restoring economic integrity are urgently called for. This paper proposes an approach based on CNN, a neural network powerful in image classification, for detecting counterfeit Indian currency notes. To train and test a CNN model, a dataset of Indian currency notes is taken from Kaggle, which contains images of real and counterfeit currency. Data preprocessing and augmentation such as rescaling and horizontal flipping were used to enhance the model generalization due to the small size of the dataset. Based on feature extraction, the CNN model has used several convolutional and pooling layers to extract high-level patterns that discriminate real from fake notes. The experiments produced an accuracy of 84.11% percent; thus, validation has shown its great promise for applications of practical counterfeit detection. Precision, recall, and F1-score were also computed to fully evaluate the model's performance, confirming deep learning can provide an efficient and automatable way toward currency verification.

Keywords: Counterfeit Currency Detection, Indian Currency Recognition, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Image Classification, Deep Learning, Binary Classification, Binary Cross-Entropy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Governments and financial institutions across the globe have long faced the challenge of detecting counterfeit currency, as counterfeit bills creep into economies and threaten their stability. Conventional counterfeit currency detection mechanisms can be lengthy, tedious, labour intensive, and expensive because they often rely on humans and/or the built-in sensitivity of elaborate physical scanning devices. More recently, however, with advances in technology and, in particular, the fields of artificial intelligence and machine learning, the establishment of automated systems that are capable of quickly detecting counterfeit is now possible. Henceforth, we proposed to use deep learning methods, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), which have gained extraordinary attention in visual tasks such as image recognition, to implement a currency detection system.

Being the best-performing deep learning architecture for any visual prediction tasks, CNN is capable of capturing the learning relationships among spatial hierarchies and may also jointly

detect different visual patterns. In contrast to other machine learning algorithms that often operate based on features painstakingly defined by humans, CNNs are capable of receiving the camera images as raw data and thus may be more suitable in use cases represented by the complexity of feature spaces encountered in counterfeit detection. For this study, we utilized CNN to classify Indian currency bills in the image data as either real or fake..

There are several other studies developed using diverse techniques for the detection of counterfeit currencies using deep learning and image processing methods; other research has tried on these various aspects. Pham [1] highlighted the smartphone camera detection of fake banknotes in the cross-dataset environment. Mukundan [2] introduced a novel hyperspectral imaging approach to counterfeit currency detection, while Pachón [3] applied deep learning methods for the recognition of fake banknotes. Kanawade [4] compared different machinelearning models for currency fraud detection and Gebremeskel [5] focused on detecting counterfeit Ethiopian banknotes using deep learning techniques. Ali [6] proposed the usage of GANs for counterfeit detection, while Ahmed [7] provided a detailed comprehensive review of the various deep learning processes in counterfeit currency recognition. Kumar [8] proposed a deep convolutional neural network for Indian currency detection, while Agasti [9] used image-processing techniques for fake currency recognition. Kumar [10] applied the Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix algorithm for the detection of fake notes. Kalla [11] developed a general counterfeit currency detection system, and Singh [12] introduced a hybrid CNN-LSTM approach for currency recognition, especially for semi-blinded and blind persons. Both Shilpa B [13] and Bhopale [14] also conducted explorations of deep learning-based approaches using various techniques for counterfeit currency detection. These studies presented together specify that there are many algorithms and approaches for the enhancement of the accuracy of counterfeit currency detection in both recognizable image processing and modern deep learning architectures.

This current paper aims to evolve a CNN model capable of automating the distinction between Indian currency notes that are real and fake with extremely high safety measures. Care is taken to use an Indian currency dataset hosted on Kaggle, which consists of images of genuine and counterfeit notes, which is already pre-labelled, which makes it a perfect dataset for use in supervised learning. A series of CNN architecture, comprising several convolutional and pooling layers, which are followed by dense layers were designed in order thoroughly to extract and analyze those features inherent to real and fake notes

The model is trained using the Indian currency dataset and used a separate test set to evaluate its generalizability to invisible data. The CNN architecture is fine tuned through optimization of hyperparameters, dropout to limit overfitting, and binary cross entropy as a loss function that facilitates the binary classification task. Very few evaluation metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, provides a flavour of how the model performs in the identification of counterfeit notes.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGIES

A. Dataset Description

The dataset for this research was drawn from the "Indian Currency Dataset" at Kaggle, comprising images of real and counterfeit Indian currency notes, particularly focusing on ₹500 and ₹2000 denominations. The dataset is structured in two directories: one for training and another for testing, wherein each directory contains two subdirectories called "real" and "fake." With 248 images total, the training set includes 120 real and 128 fake, whereas the test set contains 107 images consisting of 59 real and 48 fake notes.

Thus, the arrangement allows the model to witness a variety of samples during had been used for training so it learns the defining feature of each real and fake currency, also being subjected to its ability to generalize when tested on never-beforeseen samples. The dataset has other distinctions of texture, colour, and watermark nuances; each is a distinguishing visual feature that the model ought to learn to assign the right class. Due to the smaller number of images, techniques of data augmentation like zooming, shearing, and horizontal flipping have been instrumental in artificially inflating the dataset for better generalizability of the model. Such an arrangement provides an exciting and challenging benchmark for evaluating deep learning models on counterfeit currency note detection.

B. Pre-Processing

The pre-processing is essentially for making images ready for input into the CNN model. To match the input requirement of the CNN, all images within the dataset were set to a standard dimension of 224X224 pixels. Rescaling pixel values from 255 to a 0-1 range helped normalise data and speed up the process of training. Data enhancement techniques, including shearing, zooming, and horizontal flipping, were also applied to the training images to increase their diversity and avoid overfitting. These transformations, by simulating several real-world conditions, were made robust against variations in test data. However, rescaling only was performed for the test data without any further augmentations to avoid compromising model performance evaluation.

C. Feature Extraction

Feature extraction is the bedrock of counterfeit detection systems. In the CNNs, the feature extraction is performed by the convolution layer in which with the help of filters patterns are detected in images. A number of convolutional layers with ReLU activations were used in this model to capture certain fine details of currency notes like texture, color patterns, and other marks characteristic to each note. Each convolutional layer was followed by max-pooling layers, which reduced the spatial dimensionality of the feature maps hence increasing the computational efficiency. As a result of combining convolutional and pooling layers together, the model becomes capable of learning the high-level features that can separate the real currency notes from the counterfeits. A dropout layer was also introduced in the architecture just before entering the fully connected layers to avoid overfitting by disabling neurons with a set probability during training. These combined preprocessing and feature extraction techniques enable the system to analyse and verify the authenticity of currency notes with high accuracy in all environmental conditions.

C. Proposed Architecture

The proposed architecture for the currency note classification task is a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) designed to learn visual features and classify the currency notes as resulting from real or fake currency images. The model consists of three convolutional layers wherein each one employs an increasing number of filters: 32, 64, and 128. This characteristic enables it to capture low-level and high-level features from the input images. Thereafter, each convolutional layer is usually followed by a max-pooling layer to down-sample the feature maps. This process will prevent increasing spatial dimensions and computational complexities while retaining the germane features.

After the last convolutional layer, the output feature map will be transformed into a one-dimensional vector and then fed into a dense layer with 128 neurons activated by ReLU. The dense layer further learns higher-level abstractions from the learned features. A regularization method to avoid overfitting during training is by adding a dropout layer with the dropout rate set at 0.5. Finally, the output layer is defined as a sigmoid-activated output unit that produces a probability score spaced between 0 and 1 classifying the image as either "real" or "fake" currency. The loss function corresponding to binary classification issues is set to binary cross-entropy with an Adam optimizer, assessing its efficient performance along with its adaptive learning rates at training. The architecture is simple yet effective, allowing the model to learn discriminative features from the input images and subsequently carry out the classification task competently.

Figure 1. CNN architecture to detect real and fake currency

Figure 2: Predicted real and fake 500,2000 notes from the dataset

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Accuracy of Proposed Method CNN with Various Existing Methods

The ratio of correctly predicted by the model is called accuracy. Table 1 shows how accuracy and CNN model are compared. It is evident that the proposed CNN model, with an accuracy of 84.11%, outperforms other models like GLCM, Image Processing, Fluorescence-based methods, various sensors in terms of classification accuracy and is graphically shown in Figure 3.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (1)$$

Table 1: Accuracy Comparison of existing model with proposed CNN approach

S. No	Model Name	Accuracy (%)
1.	CNN	84.11
2.	GLCM, Image Processing [10]	83.50
3.	Fluorescence, Image Processing [29]	83.00
4.	Various Sensors, Image Processing [15]	82.00
5.	Image Processing, SVM [17]	81.00
6.	Feature Extraction, Machine Learning [27]	80.80
7.	Image Processing, SVM [9]	80.00

Figure 3. Accuracy comparison if existing models with proposes CNN approach

Precision of Proposed Method CNN with Various Existing Methods

The ratio of genuine positives to all of the model's positive predictions is known as precision. Table-2 illustrates the comparison of the precision and CNN model. It is clear that the proposed CNN model's precision of 75.41% is lower compared to methods like Fluorescence, Image Processing (82.50%) and GLCM, Image Processing (82.40%). However, it still offers reasonable precision, which indicates that it has a fairly good ability to correctly classify the positive class (real or fake currency). and depicted in the figure 4 graphically

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (2)$$

Table 2: Precision Comparison of existing model with proposed CNN approach

S.No	Model Name	Precision (%)
1.	CNN	75.41
2.	Fluorescence, Image Processing [29]	82.50
3.	GLCM, Image Processing [10]	82.40
4.	Image Processing, SVM [17]	80.50
5.	Various Sensors, Image Processing [15]	80.00
6.	Feature Extraction, Machine Learning [27]	79.50
7.	Image Processing, SVM [9]	78.00

Figure 4. Accuracy comparison if existing models with proposes CNN approach

Recall of Proposed Method CNN with Various Existing Methods

The ratio of genuine positives to actual positives is known as recall. Table-3 illustrates the comparison of the recall and CNN model. It is clear that the proposed The CNN model excels in recall, with an impressive 95.83%, indicating a highly efficient model in detecting fake or real currency notes. This outshines other models, such as GLCM, Image Processing (85.00%) and Fluorescence-based Image Processing (85.00%). The CNN's ability to correctly identify most of the true positives sets it apart from traditional methods, where recall tends to be lower.and depicted in the figure 5 graphically

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (3)$$

Table 3: Recall Comparison of existing model with proposed CNN approach

S.No	Model Name	Recall (%)
1.	CNN	95.83
2.	GLCM, Image Processing [10]	85.00
3.	Fluorescence, Image Processing [29]	85.00
4.	Various Sensors, Image Processing [15]	85.00
5.	Image Processing, SVM [17]	83.00
6.	Feature Extraction, Machine Learning [27]	83.00
7.	Image Processing, SVM [9]	82.00

Figure 5. Accuracy comparison if existing models with proposes CNN approach

F1-Score of Proposed Method CNN with Various Existing Methods

An indicator that can counterbalance the accuracy-recall trade-off is the F1-Score. The comparison between the CNN model and the F1-Score is shown in Table 4. When The CNN model has an F1-score of 84.40%, which reflects a balanced performance between precision and recall. While it is slightly higher than models like Image Processing, SVM (79.00%) and Feature Extraction (81.60%), it is not as high as the recall-driven models, such as GLCM, Image Processing (83.00%) and Fluorescence, Image Processing (83.00%) and is graphically shown in Figure 6

$$F1 - Score = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (4)$$

Table 4: F1-Score Comparison of existing model with proposed CNN approach

S.No	Model Name	F1-Score (%)
1.	CNN	84.40
2.	GLCM, Image Processing [10]	83.00
3.	Fluorescence, Image Processing [29]	83.00
4.	Various Sensors, Image Processing [15]	83.00
5.	Image Processing, SVM [17]	82.00
6.	Feature Extraction, Machine Learning [27]	81.60
7.	Image Processing, SVM [9]	79.00

Figure 6. Accuracy comparison if existing models with proposes CNN approach

Error Rate of Proposed Method CNN with Various Existing Methods

The error rate is a measure of how often a model makes incorrect predictions. Table 5 illustrates the comparison of the Error Rate and CNN model. It is clear that the CNN model with an error rate of 15.89%, the CNN model demonstrates relatively lower error compared to other algorithms. It outperforms GLCM, Image Processing (16.50%) and Fluorescence, Image Processing (17.00%). The error rate is crucial, and a lower value reflects a model's effectiveness in avoiding misclassification of currency notes and depicted in the figure graphically 7.

$$\text{Error Rate} = \frac{FP+FN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \tag{5}$$

$$\text{Error rate} = 1 - \text{Accuracy} \tag{6}$$

Table 5: Comparison of the Error Rate and CNN model

S.No	Model Name	F1-Score (%)
1.	CNN	15.89
2.	GLCM, Image Processing [10]	16.50
3.	Fluorescence, Image Processing [29]	17.00
4.	Various Sensors, Image Processing [15]	18.00
5.	Feature Extraction, Machine Learning [27]	19.20
6.	Image Processing, SVM [17]	19.00
7.	Image Processing, SVM [9]	20.00

Figure 7. Accuracy comparison if existing models with proposes CNN approach

IV. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated the worth of the CNN-based approach to counterfeit currency note detection in India, attaining an accuracy of 84.11%. The model performance has thus found its metrics: precision (75.41%), recall (95.83%), F1score (84.40%), and error rate of 15.89%, indicating the deep learning techniques' performance in real-life applications like currency detection. Data augmentation combined with the dropout layer helped minimize overfitting, ensuring the model performed well with unseen data.

The dice show the viability of automated, low-cost techniques in the perennial battle against counterfeit currency, a promising alternative to the erstwhile approaches. However, the results also suggest some areas for improvement in the light of better design of the network architecture. Future research should focus more on transfer learning, which has the potential to boost performance through the integration of pre-trained models, and on the incorporation of larger and more diverse datasets to enhance the robustness and correctness of the system.

To conclude this work, this study is putting its foot ahead toward the stand-alone currency detection devices that aim as chief parts of anti-counterfeiting efforts. These systems may give a dependable, scalable solution to the rising hurdles of monetary fraud, should they be augmented further. counterfeiting.

V. REFERENCES

- [1] Agasti, T. , (2015), "Fake Currency Detection Using Image Processing," Proceedings of the International Conference on Advanced Computing and Software Engineering.
- [2] Ahmed, T. N. , (2020), "Counterfeit Currency Recognition Using Deep Learning: A Review," Journal of Electrical Engineering & Technology, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 2579-2587.
- [3] Ali, T. , (2020), "DeepMoney: Counterfeit Money Detection Using Generative Adversarial Networks," IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 212204-212214.
- [4] Alex, D. S. , Subramanian, P. , Subashini, S. , Kumaresan, T. , Stalin, B. , (2017), "Counterfeit Currency Detection Based on Fluorescence in HSV Color Space," International Journal of Computer Science and Engineering, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 245-250.
- [5] Bhopale, V. , (2018), "Fake Currency Detection Using Deep Learning," Proceedings of the International Conference on Data Science and Applications.
- [6] Bandu, S. C. D. , Kakileti, M. , (2019), "Indian Fake Currency Detection Using Image Processing and Machine Learning," International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 250-255.
- [7] Babu, A. , Sankar, V. , (2018), "Fake Indian Currency Detection," International Journal of Applied Engineering Research, vol. 13, no. 7, pp. 6003-6007.
- [8] D. N. R., (2018). "A Review on Fake Currency Detection Using Feature Extraction," International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 46-51.
- [9] Gebremeskel, G. , (2017), "Developing a Model for Detection of Ethiopian Fake Banknote Using Deep Learning," International Journal of Computer Applications, vol. 174, no. 8, pp. 36-41.
- [10] Jahan Nahin, I. , Sunzida, S. H. , (2017), "Fake Currency Detection," International Journal of Computer Applications, vol. 175, no. 3, pp. 23-28.
- [11] Kalla, G. , (2019), "Counterfeit Currency Detection," International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 101-106.
- [12] Kumar, S. N. , (2021), "A Novel Approach for Detection of Counterfeit Indian Currency Notes Using Deep Convolutional Neural Network," Journal of Imaging, vol. 7, no. 11, pp. 211.
- [13] Lee, J. W. et al., (2017), "A Survey on Banknote Recognition Method by Various Sensors," Sensors, vol. 17, no. 7, pp. 1565-1576.
- [14] Lalitha, M. R. , Krishna, S. (2018), "Fake Currency Detection Using Image Processing," International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 98-103.
- [15] Keerthana, G. V. , (2019), "Fake Currency Detection Using Deep Learning," Proceedings of the International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Machine Learning.

- [16] Kanawade, S. B. , (2015), "Counterfeit Currency Detection Using Machine Learning," International Journal of Computer Applications, vol. 111, no. 16, pp. 24-28.
- [17] Mattaparthi, S. , Kumar, S, Yalawar, M. S. , (2020), "Fake Currency Detection: A Survey on Different Methodologies Using Machine Learning Techniques," Journal of Artificial Intelligence & Data Mining, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 121-131.
- [18] Meshram, V. , Patil, K., (2018), "Dataset of Indian and Thai Banknotes with Annotations," Journal of Computer Vision and Image Processing, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 18-23.
- [19] Mukundan, A. ,(2017), "Automatic Counterfeit Currency Detection Using a Novel Snapshot Hyperspectral Imaging Algorithm," Journal of Applied Remote Sensing, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 026028.
- [20] Naveen Kumar, T. , Subhash,t, (2018), "Fake Currency Recognition System for Indian Notes Using Image Processing Techniques," International Journal of Engineering and Technology, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 1030-1036.
- [21] Pham, T. D. , Lee Y. W. , Park C. and Park K. R,(2022), "Deep Learning-Based Detection of Fake Multinational Banknotes in a Cross-Dataset Environment Utilizing Smartphone Cameras for Assisting Visually Impaired Individuals," Mathematics, vol. 10, no. 9, pp. 1616..
- [22] Pachón, C. G. , (2021), "Fake Banknote Recognition Using Deep Learning," Neural Computing and Applications, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 1449-1461.
- [23] Siva Sai Kumar, A. S. , (2013), "Detection of Fake Currency Note Using Gray-Level Co-Occurrence Matrix Algorithm," International Journal of Computer Applications, vol. 5, no. 9, pp. 9-15.
- [24] Singh, K. , (2020), "Currency Recognition System for Visually Impaired Using a Novel CNN-LSTM Based Hybrid Approach," IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 89324-89334.
- [25] S. B.,(2018), "Fake Currency Detection Using Deep Learning," Journal of Computer Science, vol. 15, no. 12, pp. 2015-2020.
- [26] Sarkar, A. , Verma, R. , Gupta, G. , (2019), "Detecting Counterfeit Currency and Identifying Its Source," IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement, vol. 68, no. 10, pp. 3645-3654.
- [27] Sasikumar, A. S. Dr. M.,(2016), "Fake Currency Detection," International Journal of Electronics and Communication Engineering, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 56-61.
- [28] Shobha Rani, B. R. , Bharathi, S. , Pareek, P. K. , Dipeeka,(2018) "Fake Currency Identification System Using Convolutional Neural Network," International Journal of Innovative Research in Computer and Communication Engineering, vol. 6, no. 12, pp. 1899-1904.
- [29] Sandeep, G. , Sikharam,, J. , (2014), "Evaluation of Machine Learning Algorithms for the Detection of Fake Bank Currency," International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering, vol. 4, no. 10, pp. 442-450.

- [30] Vijaykumar, P. , S. G., (2017), "IoT-Based Smart Wallet Security and Fake Currency Detection System," International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 302-309.